

On The Fate of Intellectuals Exiled To the Central Asian Labor Camp

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ABSTRACT

The inhuman policy pursued by the Soviet authorities in the 1930s throughout the Soviet Union, known as the "Great Terror" and the "Red Terror", resulted in the tragic death of millions of innocent people. The main goal of the Soviets was to use their intelligence and labor to imprison dissidents, intellectuals living in different regions of the USSR, by force and unjust accusations. Prisoners were mainly involved in heavy labor-intensive work, such as large-scale construction, canal digging, construction of hydroelectric power stations, work in factories, and working in state and collective farm fields.

KEYWORDS: Stalin, NKVD (People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs), GULAG (General Directorate of Forced Labor Camps), Great terror, Red terror, anti-Soviet idea, accusation, arrest, trial, sentence, punishment, labor camp, famine, hard labor, death.

INTRODUCTION

The inhuman policy pursued by the Soviet authorities in the 1930s throughout the Soviet Union, known as the "Great Terror" and the "Red Terror", resulted in the tragic death of millions of innocent people. The main goal of the Soviets was to use their intelligence and labor to imprison dissidents, intellectuals living in different regions of the USSR, by force and unjust accusations. Prisoners were mainly involved in heavy labor-intensive work, such as large-scale construction, canal digging, construction of hydroelectric power stations, work in factories, and working in state and collective farm fields.

The Central Asian Labor and Correctional Camp (Sazlag) was established in 1930 in Tashkent to implement the government's decision to attract labor to use natural resources in remote areas. In the operational command, the Central Asian camp was subordinated to the Central Asian Plenipotentiary Representation of the OGPU (United State Political Administration), and then to the NKVD GULAG. In 1930-1934, the Central Asian labor camp was almost the worst camp in the USSR. On July 29, 1939, the Central Asian labor camp was transformed into the NKVD colony administration of the USSR [5]. The maximum number of prisoners held here was recorded on January 1, 1938, and amounted to 33,936. The Central Asian labor camp closed in 1943. Here the labor of the captives was mainly used in state farms (cotton growing), in agricultural work in the maintenance of cotton mills, in the camps' own enterprises, in the production of land reclamation and consumer goods. In

1930, the prisoners of the camp also carried out loading and unloading operations for water transport in the Aral Sea.

MAIN PART

Sazlag had a large number of prisoners from the Central Asian republics and various regions of the USSR, including those who had a significant place in the USSR in the field of science and education: Bukharin Vladimir Ivanovich, Valyashko Mikhail Georgievich, Voznesenskiy Alexander Nikolaevich, Derevitskiy Alexey Petrovich, Durnovo Andrey Nikolaevich, Kravtsov Nikolay Ivanovich, Lichkov Boris Leonidovich, Matorin Nikolai Mikhailovich[3]. Keeping prisoners, providing them with food and shelter has become extremely difficult. Therefore, some of the prisoners were forced to be sent to other camps in the GULAG system. Among the prisoners named above was **Vladimir Ivanovich Bukharin**, the brother of Nikolai Ivanovich Bukharin, a prominent political figure and Bolshevik leader. He was born in 1890 in Moscow to an educated family. From 1900 to 1914 Komissarov studied at the Classical School No. 7, then in the Department of Mechanics of the Higher Technical School. He took part in the First World War in 1914-1917 and was wounded, and was awarded the St. George's Cross for his bravery in battle. After the war he worked in various positions in manufacturing factories until 1938, but was arrested on November 3, 1938. In January 1939, by a special decision of the NKVD, he was accused of spreading anti-Soviet ideas and sent to a labor-correctional camp for 8 years. The NKVD decides to send Bukharin to SazLAG, given his highly qualified specialization. Until 1941, he was in the camp No.

1 at the Yangiyul station in Tashkent region, where he was involved in the design and training of workers in the workshop for the production of wool and yarn. On November 9, 1941, he was transferred to the 3rd Division of Sazlag (Yalangach). He stayed there until 1946, when he set up work in a textile factory. He was released on the occasion of the expiration of his sentence in 1946, but was re-arrested on the way without any grounds and returned to the Naked Camp for unknown reasons and charges, thus remaining in the camp until 1955. In 1955, V.I. Bukharin was sent to his family, who were living in a forced labor settlement in the village of Konezavod, Kustanai Oblast, under the control of the State Security Service. In 1962 he returned to Moscow with his family and in 1964 was rehabilitated. The tragic life of Vladimir Ivanovich Bukharin comes to an end in 1980. He will be buried in Dolgoprudnensky Cemetery in Moscow Oblast.

Professor of the Institute of Physical and Chemical Analysis at the USSR Academy of Sciences **Valyashko Mikhail Georgievich** was born on September 12, 1907 in Kharkov in the family of a professor of medicine. In 1930 he graduated from the Faculty of Chemistry of the Leningrad Polytechnic Institute, was a student of Professor V.I. Nikolaev and Academician N.S. Kurnakov. From 1929 he took part in scientific expeditions to the salt lakes of Crimea, Kulunda Desert, Inder Lake and others. On January 5, 1934, he was arrested without cause. On March 29, 1934, he was convicted at an extraordinary meeting of the OGPU board and sentenced to 5 years of labor camp. Sazlag is designated as a place of execution. He was released early on November 25, 1937. From December 1937 to 1957 he worked as an employee of the All-Russian Research Institute of Gallurgy (Leningrad). During the war, he volunteered as a member of the military and participated in battles. In 1943 he defended his dissertation on "Study of the physicochemical regime of Lake Inder and the extraction of salts from its salts." On March 4, 1944 he was awarded the Order of the Red Banner of Labor. On November 28, 1956, he was rehabilitated by the Military Tribunal of the Leningrad Military District. In 1957 he defended his doctoral dissertation on "Geochemical laws of formation of potassium salt deposits." For his work of the same name, published in 1962, the USSR Academy of Sciences V. I. He will be awarded the Vernadsky Prize. From 1960 to 1984 he was a professor of geochemistry at Moscow State University, lectured on "Geochemistry of natural waters", "Geochemistry of halogenesis." From 1967 to 1983 he was the scientific director of the "Experimental Laboratory of Experimental Geochemistry" of the Faculty of Geology. President of the International Commission on Water Quality (1971-1980), Chairman of the Commission on Natural Water Geochemistry of the International Association of Geochemistry and Cosmochemistry (1970-1983). He has published more than 200 scientific papers on halogenesis and geochemistry of natural waters. He died on October 7, 1984

in Moscow. He was buried in Proletar pos., Serpukhov district, Moscow region [3].

Russian and Belarusian Soviet literary critic, writer, professor **Voznesensky Alexander Nikolaevich** was born on July 5 (17) 1888 in the village of Chukali, Simbirsk region. In 1913 he graduated from the Slavic-Russian department of the Faculty of History and Philology of the University of Warsaw and intended to study for a professorship. He worked as an assistant professor at the Faculty of History and Philology of Rostov University. From 1921 to 1927 he was an associate professor, and from 1927 to 1930 a professor at the Belarusian State University. Later, A.S. He worked at the Moscow City Pedagogical Institute named after Bubnov, Moscow Institute of Cinematography, People's Commissariat of Heavy Industry. On February 13, 1934, he was arrested on suspicion of counter-revolutionary propaganda (Article 58-4-10-11 of the Criminal Code of the RSFSR) and on March 29, 1934, he was found guilty by the OGPU board. He was transferred to Sazlag to serve a five-year prison sentence. After his release on February 10, 1939, he was a professor at the Kazan Pedagogical Institute, and from 1943 to 1947 he was the dean of the Faculty of History and Philology of Kazan University. In 1944 he defended his doctoral dissertation in Kazan on "Research on the history of modern Belarusian literature." He developed a tradition of academic literary criticism. He analyzed the works of M. Bogdanovich, J. Kupala, J. Kolas from a comparative typological point of view, in the context of European literature. On August 4, 1945, all charges against Voznesensky were dropped, and on October 26, 1964, he was rehabilitated by the Presidium of the Moscow City Court. He died in 1966 [3].

Derevitsky Alexei Petrovich was born on August 7, 1896 in St. Petersburg in a noble family. In 1914 he graduated from the Kiev Cadet School. In 1915, after graduating from artillery school, Konstantinov was sent to World War I. The last military rank he received was Captain Staff. After the revolution he served in the Red Army in 1919-1922 and 1932-1933. On April 26, 1935, he was arrested in Moscow along with his sister Ekaterina and her husband Nikolai Velyaminov. He was accused of being a member of a counter-revolutionary group of "former people" consisting of representatives of the White Guard emigration, allegedly organized by brother-in-law Velyaminov, in a state of terror against the Soviet government. On June 9, 1935, by a special decision of the NKVD, he was exiled to the Central Asian labor camp (Sazlag) for 3 years. After serving his sentence, he lived in the Vologda region until 1941 and worked in the statistics department of the district consumer association. In the summer of 1943, he commanded a mortar regiment under the rank of major on the battlefields of World War II. VS was awarded the Order of the I degree in accordance with the Order of the Front No. 125 / n of August 20, 1943 of the Voronezh Front. Rehabilitated on January 30, 1957 by the Supreme Court of the USSR. Archive case: R-11240 (CA FSB RF) [6].

Andrei Nikolaevich Durnovo, a scientist who studied the languages, literature, folklore, history, material and spiritual culture of the Slavic peoples, was born in 1910 in Moscow in the family of philologist Nikolai Nikolaevich Durnovo. In 1926 he graduated from high school, then the faculty of history and philology of Moscow State University, a Slavic by profession. After graduating, he worked as a literary critic. Andrei was arrested with his father on December 28, 1933. Like his father, he was accused of "counter-revolutionary activities and membership in an anti-Soviet organization - the Russian National Party." In addition to the father and son Durnovo, more than 100 people took part in the so-called "Slavic affair." Among those arrested were academics M.N. Speranskiy, V.N. Perets, Corresponding Members of the Academy of Sciences G.A. Ilinskiy, A.M. Selishchev and other well-known Soviet scholars: well-known art critics, anthropologists, linguists, literary critics, philologists, architects, restorers, musicologists, as well as agronomists, doctors, museum staff. Particular attention was paid to the case of "members of the Russian National Party" in Moscow and Leningrad. According to the indictment prepared by the investigation, there is a widespread counter-revolutionary national-fascist organization in Moscow, Leningrad, Ukraine, Azov, the Black Sea region, Belarus, the West and Ivanovo regions which was called "Russian National Party" and set the goal of overthrowing Soviet rule and establishing a fascist dictatorship in the country. The Russian National Party unites in its ranks various nationalist elements with a common interest in the struggle against Soviet rule. The RNP counter-revolutionary organization was formed under the direct direction of the Russian fascist center headed by Prince N.S. Trubetsky, P.O. Yakobson, P. G. Bogatirev and others. Andrei, unlike his father, was influenced by the Eurasian ideas of the Russian linguist N.S. Trubetsky. During a search of the Durnovo house, fragments from Trubetsky's books and Andrei's notebook were found and confiscated. Another "thread" that tied Andrei to Trubetsky was Varvara, the nephew of his future wife, N.S. Trubetsky. On March 29, 1934, Andrei Nikolaevich Durnovo was sentenced to five years in labor camps (on the same day his father was sentenced to 10 years in labor camps). Both were sent to serve their sentences in Solovki. He was later transferred to Andrei Sazlag, where he was re-tried and shot on January 5, 1938. He was 28 years old. Andrei Nikolaevich Durnovo was rehabilitated on October 26, 1964 by the Presidium of the Moscow City Court [6].

Soviet Slavic literary critic, professor at Moscow State University, translator of the Serbian language **Kravtsov Nikolai Ivanovich** was born on June 24, 1906 in the village of Orekhovo, Kamyshinsky district, Nizhnevolzhsk region. After graduating from high school in 1923, he entered the Moscow Institute of Language and Literature, and in 1925 graduated from the Department of Linguistics. In 1926 he was admitted to the literature department of the Faculty of History and Ethnology of Moscow University as a second-year

student, graduating in 1929 with a degree in Russian and Western Studies. From 1929 to 1932 he worked as an editor at the State Publishing House of Fiction (GIXL). On January 11, 1934, he was arrested on suspicion of counter-revolutionary propaganda. On March 29, 1934, he was tried by the OGPU board, found guilty under Articles 58-10, 58-11 of the Criminal Code of the RSFSR, and sentenced to 5 years in a labor camp. He will be sent to Sazlag to serve his sentence. He will be involved in field work at the Malik state farm near Tashkent. He was released on October 20, 1938. After his release he lived in Tambov. In 1939 he was admitted to the Tambov State Pedagogical Institute as a senior lecturer at the Department of History of Russian Literature. On July 7, 1947, the charges against him were dropped. Until 1960 (with a short break in 1941-1942) he worked as the head of the department of Russian language and literature. In 1966, under his leadership, Tambov philologists wrote a textbook "History of Russian literature in the second half of the XIX century", which was published by Prosveshchenie. In parallel, from 1947 he worked at the Institute of Slavic Studies of the USSR Academy of Sciences. In the 1960s and 1980s, M.A. V. He headed the Department of Folklore at Lomonosov Moscow State University. On October 26, 1964, he was rehabilitated by the Presidium of the Moscow City Court. He died on September 9, 1980 in Moscow [3, 1].

Russian and Soviet geologist, hydrogeologist, professor, co-founder and director of the Ukrainian Geological Committee, repressed geologist **Lichkov Boris Leonidovich** was born on July 19, 1888 in the Irkutsk region in the family of statistician Leonid Semenovich Lichkov. After graduating from the Kiev-Pechersk Gymnasium in 1906, he entered the Department of Natural Sciences, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics, St. Vladimir University, graduating in 1912. He was the first director of the Geological Committee of Ukraine, then deputy director (1918-1927), head of the groundwater department of the Institute of Hydrology in Leningrad (1924-1934). He was arrested by the OGPU board on January 5, 1934, and on March 29, 1934, was convicted of counter-revolutionary propaganda (Article 58-7-10-11 of the RSFSR Criminal Code) and sentenced to 10 years in a labor camp. He first worked as a hydrologist in Sazlag, from November 1934 in the construction of the Moscow-Volga canal in Dmitlag, and from the end of 1935 in the construction of the Rybinsk HPP in Volgalag. At the end of 1939 he was released from prison prematurely and left the camp on November 6, 1939, but until February 1941 he undertook to participate in the construction of the Rybinsk HPP. Then he worked in Samarkand, from 1942 in Stalinabad (Dushanbe). In 1945, his conviction was overturned. In 1946, he returned to Leningrad, where he worked as the head of the hydrology department at Leningrad State University. Professor since 1948, Doctor of Geological and Mineralogical Sciences (1943). Lichkov, who went down in history as an honorary member of the USSR Geographical Society (since 1962), was rehabilitated on November 28,

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1956 by the Military Tribunal of the Leningrad Military District. The scientist died on October 20, 1966 in Leningrad (St. Petersburg) [2].

Researcher of the USSR Academy of Sciences, Professor **Matorin Nikolai Mikhailovich** was born in 1898 in the village of Pervitino, Tver region, in a family of nobles. In 1916 he graduated from the Imperial Nikolaevskaya Tsarskoselovskaya Gymnasium with a silver medal and entered the Faculty of History and Philology of the University of Petrograd. There he becomes interested in the history of ancient societies. He was called up for military service in 1917 and returned home after the October Revolution. He accepted the ideas of the revolution with all his heart and remained faithful until his death. In March 1919 he joined the RKP (b) and then spent three years in Soviet and party affairs in Gdov, and from July 1922 in Petrograd the chairman of the Petrograd Soviet G. E. He worked as Zinovev's secretary. From 1924 he lectured at the Faculty of Geography of Leningrad State University. From 1923 to 1925 he was a researcher at the Marxist Research Institute and played an important role in the Leningrad party organization. After the defeat of Zinovev at the XIV Congress of the Party (1925), he was sent to work in the public education authorities of the Pskov region, where he continued his scientific work, writing lyrical poems. In 1927 he moved to Kazan, where he wrote his first major scientific work, "Religion among the peoples of the Volga-Kama region: before and now. Idolatry. Islam. Orthodoxy. Sectarianism" (M., 1929). In September 1928, Nikolai Matorin returned to Leningrad with an offer to teach as an associate professor at the Department of Ethnography, Faculty of Geography, Leningrad State University, under the guidance of Professor V.G. Bogoraz. Since then, Matorin has focused more on scientific and organizational work in the field of ethnography. In January 1929 he was appointed head of the ethnographic department of the State Academy of History of Material Culture (GAIMK), a member of the Methodological Bureau of this academy. In January 1930, he was approved as Deputy Chairman of the Institute for the Study of Nations (IPIN) on the recommendation of academician N.Ya. Marr. Here he works as the head of the department, the head of the Russian sector, the head of the European department. Matorin significantly intensified the team work on the study of religious beliefs and syncretism, the culture of life in the modern village, the activities of the expedition. In October 1930, Matorin was elected director of the Peter the Great Museum of Anthropology and Ethnography. By 1931, Matorin was a professor, a leading expert in theology, and had lectured at several educational institutions, including the Leningrad State Institute of History and Linguistics (LILI). From 1933 Matorin was director of the Institute of Anthropology and Ethnography. On

December 29, 1934, the party committee of the USSR Academy of Sciences expelled Matorin from the KPSS (b) as a former oppositionist who had "not severed ideological ties with the counter-revolutionary Zinovev opposition." On the night of January 2, 1935, Matorin was arrested. On January 15, 1935, by the decision of the Presidium of the USSR Academy of Sciences, he was removed from all positions. Camp conditions were relatively mild at the time, N.C. M. Matorin was allowed to continue his scientific activities, subscribe to books, and write articles. On February 13, 1935, by an extraordinary meeting of the NKVD of the USSR, he was sentenced to 5 years in labor camps "for counter-revolutionary activities", which he spent in the Sazlag state farm "Malik". In conversations with prisoners, he collected materials on religious beliefs, religious culture and daily life of Islam, worked on his doctoral dissertation "Religious Syncretism", developed programs for the study of Muslim beliefs, wrote an article in the journal "Historical Source of Folklore." Sazlag sent it to the Academy of Sciences for publication in the Soviet Ethnography. He has worked on a number of articles on shamanism, Orthodoxy, Islam, ancient beliefs based on materials from the Oryol region. On February 18, 1936, he was transferred from Tashkent to Leningrad, closer to Moscow, where the August trial of Kamenev and Zinovev was being prepared. On October 11, 1936, a traveling session of the Military Board of the Supreme Court of the USSR, chaired by V. Ulrich, sentenced him to death. N. M. Matorin was shot the same day. On March 20, 1958, N.C. M. The verdict against Matorin was overturned by the Military Chamber of the Supreme Court of the USSR due to the lack of criminal content.¹ From the above it is clear that the Bolsheviks valued neither man nor science. However, their knowledge was used to dig canals, run production in factories, and organize irrigation work in the fields. It is noteworthy that all of them, being members of the Communist Party, were persecuted on the same charges. The trial of 6 of the 9 scientists mentioned above took place on the same day - March 29, 1934.

In all, there were hundreds of thousands of engineers and scientists in the Gulag system. The names of many of them are still unknown, as the archives of the Soviet penitentiary system are still secret and only close relatives of the persecuted can access the information.

Most of those repressed during the Great Terror were rehabilitated after the death of Joseph Stalin, and some after their own deaths.

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